

Some Interesting Sesquiterpene Lactones*

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Among the sesquiterpenes, the lactonic members form a very large group. Because of the complexity of their structures and the reactions and rearrangements which they undergo, they have attracted the attention of very eminent chemists during the last half a century or so. The lactones occur widely. The plants of the *Compositae* family are known to be very rich in lactones. Many of the members of this family are available in India, especially in the Northern Himalayan regions. In this lecture I am going to discuss the reactions and structural features of some of these lactones isolated from indigenous sources.

A well-known plant of the *Compositae* family, which occurs in India, is the costus plant (*Saussurea lappa*, Clark). It grows in the upper regions of the Punjab and Kashmir at an altitude of 10,000 ft. and above. The roots have been known for their medicinal properties and contain a highly odorous oil. Though several competent scientists have worked on the chemical constituents of costus root at different stages, the actual isolation of the lactonic constituents in quantity has been possible only after the development of the low temperature solvent extraction procedure¹. Such a procedure was necessary because of the thermo-labile nature of some of the lactones which, almost invariably, contain a conjugated lactonic function. Alongwith other constituents, costus roots contain² costunolide (I), dihydrocostunolide (II), dehydrocostus lactone (III) and saussurea lactone (IV). Costunolide has somewhat unusual structural features, containing a 10-membered carbocyclic system with a conjugated α -methylene, γ -lactone moiety. It is a member of the germacrone³ group (V).

Costunolide can be considered on bigenetic grounds to be the precursor of the lactones of the santonene series (VI). In this context mention should be made of its easy cyclization to santenolides and related products⁴. The structure and stereochemistry of costunolide have been thoroughly established by chemical degradation and application of spectral methods⁵. I shall not dilate on these details in this lecture but would only try to indicate

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1. A. Paul, A. S. Bawdekar, R. S. Joshi, G. H. Kulkarni, A. S. Rao, G. R. Kelkar and S. C. Bhattacharyya, *Perf. and Ess. Oil. Rec.*, 1960, **51**, 115.
2. G. H. Kulkarni, A. S. Bawdekar, A. S. Rao, G. R. Kelkar and S. C. Bhattacharyya, *Perf. and Ess. Oil. Rec.*, 1963, **54**, 303.
3. V. Herout, M. Horak, B. Schensneider and F. Soum, *Chem. and Ind.*, 1959, **35**, 1089.
4. A. M. Shaligram, A. S. Rao and S. C. Bhattacharyya, *Tetrahedron*, 1962, **18**, 969.
5. A. S. Rao, G. R. Kelkar and S. C. Bhattacharyya, *Tetrahedron*, 1960, **9**, 275.

some of the other reactions which are of typical structural interest. Costunolide can be easily hydrogenated to dihydrocostunolide (II). The latter undergoes cyclization in the

FIGURE 1

presence of acidic catalyst to α -cyclodihydrocostunolide (VII) and β -cyclodihydrocostunolide (VIII). These two products can be hydrogenated to santanolide-C (IX) and santanolide-A (X), both of which can also be obtained in several stages from the well-known sesquiterpene lactone santonin (VI). The cyclization of dihydrocostunolide in the presence of

FIG. 2

N-bromosuccinimide leads to the formation of other interesting lactones (XI)⁶. Costunolide itself can be cyclized to α -cyclocostunolide (XII) and β -cyclocostunolide (XIII).

Because of the presence of α -methylene- γ -lactone function, costunolide undergoes Michael addition with ammonia and substituted amines and also alcohols (XIV, XV)⁷. The elucidation of the structure of costunolide/dihydrocostunolide has also been helpful in deciding the stereochemistry of another naturally occurring lactone parthenolide (XVI)⁸. Both parthenolide and dihydrocostunolide (II) give the same diepoxy lactone (XVIII), establishing their mutual relationship.

FIGURE 3

As a germacrone derivative, dihydrocostunolide undergoes facile rearrangement on pyrolysis to saussurea lactone (IV)⁹. This is reminiscent of the conversion of germacrone (V) to pyrogermacrone (XIX). Saussurea lactone has been isolated from costus root oil. Careful examination of the fractions of costus root oil in which this lactone is likely to occur shows that saussurea lactone is not an actual constituent of the oil but an artifact and is

6. T. C. Jain, C. M. Banks and J. E. McCloskey (personal communication).
7. G. H. Kulkarni, G. R. Kelkar and S. C. Bhattacharyya, *Tetrahedron*, 1964, **20**, 1301.
8. A. S. Bawdekar, G. R. Kelkar and S. C. Bhattacharyya, *Tetrahedron, Letters*, 1966, No. 11, 1225.
9. A. S. Rao, A. Paul, Sadgopal and S. C. Bhattacharyya, *Tetrahedron*, 1961, **13**, 319.

formed via pyrolysis of dihydrocostunolide, which is a naturally occurring constituent of the oil. Saussurea lactone is a member of the elemene groups of sesquiterpenes (XX). The structure and stereochemistry of saussurea lactone has been established by cyclization to santanolide-C (IX) and also by a direct synthesis of saussurea lactone and tetrahydrosaussurea lactone (XXI) from santonin (VI)^{10, 11}.

FIGURE 4

Costunolide and saussurea lactone have been very helpful in deciding the stereochemistry of several other interesting sesquiterpenes. Thus, β -santanolide (VIII) and the corresponding dihydrocompound santanolide-C (IX), by modified lithiumaluminium hydride reduction, followed by Wolf-Kishner reduction can be converted to (+) junenol (XXII), and (+) dihydrojunenol (XXIII). Identity of the products, thus obtained, via synthetic routes, with the naturally occurring junenol and its dihydro derivative, also helped in deciding the absolute stereochemistry of the antipodal sesquiterpene (-) junenol (XXIV), which occurs in certain specimens of Indian vetiver oil⁴.

On the other hand, when the sesquiterpene elemol is hydrogenated to tetrahydroelemol (XXV) and pyrolysed in the form of its benzoate, it yields tetrahydroelemene (XXVI). This on hydroboration/oxidation yields a primary alcohol (XXVII). This alcohol on treatment with leadtetraacetate forms an oxide (XXVIII) which on oxidation with chromic acid leads

10. A. S. Rao, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1969, 7 (3), 307.

11. D. M. Simonovic, A. S. Rao and S. C. Bhattacharyya, *Tetrahedron*, 1963, 19, 1061.

to tetrahydroaussurea lactone¹² (XXI). This conversion completely established the stereochemistry of elemol by a simple and elegant method.

FIGURE. 5

The stereochemistry of the santonin molecule has been a matter of interest for many chemists. Most of the relevant information were clarified and correctly interpreted during the period 1940-60. One small point on which a clear conclusion could not be drawn was the stereochemistry of the 'C'-11 methyl group. This was finally decided by the X-ray crystallography of a suitable santonin derivative¹³. A chemical proof could be provided on the basis of certain transformation products (XXIX) of dihydrocostunolide¹⁴. Conclusions drawn from this reactions-sequence clearly agree with the evidence of the X-ray crystallographer. Costunolide also undergoes several other rearrangements which are depicted below. It can be converted to guaiane derivative (XXXII) via simple reactions¹⁵. It will thus be evident that costunolide is a very versatile molecule. It may be incidentally

12. A. D. Wagh, S. K. Paknikar and S. C. Bhattacharyya, *Tetrahedron*, 1964, **20**, 2647.

13. J. D. M. Asher and G. A. Sim, *Proc. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 111.

14. R. S. Joshi, G. H. Kulkarni, G. R. Kelkar and S. C. Bhattacharyya, *Tetrahedron*, 1966, **22**, 2331.

15. S. V. Hiremath, G. H. Kulkarni, G. R. Kelkar and S. C. Bhattacharyya, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1968, **6**, 243.

mentioned that hexahydrocostunolide (XXXIII) obtained via hydrogenation of costunolide has an exaltolide (XXXIV) type occur. Both these lactones contain ring systems, larger than the usual sizes.

FIGURE 6

Dehydrocostus lactone (III), which also occurs in costus root oil as its major lactonic constituent, is a very interesting compound. It is one of the simplest of the guaianolides.

FIGURE 7

in the plant, along with large proportion of alantolactone, isoalantolactone and the corresponding dihydro derivatives. It is thus interesting to note that both the parent lactones of the santanolide and the alantolide groups,—costunolide and inunolide—, occur in the compositae plants of Indian origin. Alantolides can be subjected to a series of interesting transformations. It is of interest to note the one step synthesis of isotelekin (XXXXII) via selenium dioxide oxidation of isoalantolactone (XXXVIII)¹⁸. The conjugated lactones of this group form the usual derivatives with ammonia, alcohol etc. There are many other structural features of these lactones which could be discussed but due to paucity of time it will not be possible to do so at this stage.